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Ethical and Cultural Aspects of Dark Tourism in Azerbaijan

Abstract

The article examines the ethical and culturological aspects of dark tourism objects in Azerbaijan and discusses various issues in this area. The aim is to understand the process of preserving national memory and forming collective identity through memorial sites and historical monuments in Azerbaijan. The research was conducted on objects such as the Alley of Martyrs, the Khojaly Monument, and the January 20 Memorial, and included analyses of the ethical messages and visual symbols that these objects present to visitors. The study applied symbolic interpretation and text analysis methods. Visual and textual elements in memorial objects were analyzed with a semiotic approach, focusing on the role of these objects in collective memory and national identity. Artificial intelligence software was used to check grammatical rules in the translation and to ensure compliance with these rules. In addition, support from artificial intelligence programs was received in terms of anticipating requirements when compiling a bibliographic description of the cited literature.

Keywords: Dark tourism, Ethical issues, Culturological aspects, Memorial objects, Collective memory, National identity

Azerbaycan'da Karanlık Turizmin Etik ve Kültürel Yönleri

Öz

Bu makale, Azerbaycan'daki karanlık turizm nesnelерinin etik ve kültürel yönlerini incelemekte ve bu alandaki çeşitli konuları tartışmaktadır. Amaç, Azerbaycan'daki anma mekanları ve tarihi anıtlar aracılığıyla ulusal hafızayı koruma ve kolektif kimlik oluşturma sürecini anlamaktır. Araştırma, Şehitler Sokağı, Hocalı Anıtı ve 20 Ocak Anıtı gibi nesnelер

üzerinde yürütülmüş ve bu nesnelere ziyaretçilere sunduğu etik mesajların ve görsel sembollerin analizini içermiştir. Çalışmada sembolik yorumlama ve metin analizi yöntemleri uygulanmıştır. Anıt nesnelindeki görsel ve metinsel unsurlar, bu nesnelere kolektif hafıza ve ulusal kimlikteki rolüne odaklanan semiyotik bir yaklaşımla analiz edilmiştir. Çeviride dilbilgisi kurallarını kontrol etmek ve bu kurallara uygunluğu sağlamak için yapay zekâ yazılımları kullanıldı. Ayrıca, atıfta bulunulan literatürün bibliyografik açıklamasını derlerken gereksinimleri öngörme açısından yapay zeka programlarından destek alındı.

Anahtar Kelimeler: *Karanlık turizm, Etik konular, Kültürel yönler, Anıt objeler, Kolektif bellek, Ulusal kimlik*

Introduction

The diversification trends observed in the global tourism industry in recent decades have led to the emergence and development of different forms of tourism. In this context, dark tourism (black tourism, mourning tourism), which is one of the more unconventional and emotionally charged types of tourism, draws attention.

Dark tourism involves trips to places that hold painful memories of death, tragedy, and humanity. This concept was first used in the academic literature in 1996 by John Lennon (2000) and has since been increasingly discussed in academic circles and the tourism sector. The main goal of dark tourism is to inform visitors about the traumatic events of the past, preserve the traces of these events in human memory, and protect history from distortion by creating both individual and collective empathy. This form of tourism, while fulfilling the function of education and memory preservation on the one hand, also raises serious ethical and cultural debates on the other. Visitors' attitudes to disaster sites, their behavior in these places, and the reactions of local communities to this form of tourism necessitate the study of dark tourism not only as a tourism practice, but also as a social and cultural phenomenon. Interest in dark tourism continues to grow globally. In particular, Holocaust museums, war memorials, natural disaster sites, and terrorist attack sites are known as the main targets of dark tourism. For example, the Auschwitz-Birkenau camp in Poland, the September 11 memorial complex in the United States, the Hiroshima Memorial Park in Japan, and the Tuol Sleng Genocide Museum in Cambodia can be cited as international examples in this field. These places not only remind us of history, but also encourage empathy and reflection on human rights among people. All this makes dark tourism not only a travel experience, but also a carrier of social learning and humanitarian responsibility.

In Azerbaijan, dark tourism has begun to develop as a relatively new field. The January 20, 1990 tragedy, the Khojaly genocide, the consequences of the Karabakh wars, as well as

the restoration process in the liberated territories, are assessed as potential objects of dark tourism. The transformation of these places into tourist attractions is of great importance not only in terms of increasing the country's tourism revenues, but also in terms of preserving national identity, strengthening collective memory, and conveying historical truths to the international community. The development of dark tourism in Azerbaijan also requires maintaining a balance from an ethical and cultural perspective. There is a danger of commercialization of war and tragedy sites and the transformation of interest in these places into exploitation. Therefore, respect for national and spiritual values, elegant presentation forms, and the participation of local communities are important factors in the formation of dark tourism objects. Along with ethical approaches, consideration of the cultural context is necessary for the proper management of these sensitive issues in the field of tourism. The main purpose of this article is to analyze the current state of dark tourism in Azerbaijan, its development prospects, and the ethical and cultural aspects of this process.

The main questions of the research are as follows:

- How is the concept of dark tourism understood in Azerbaijan and in what directions is it being developed?
- What are the existing dark tourism venues in Azerbaijan and what ethical frameworks are taken into account in their presentation?
- What risks can the use of dark tourism for commercial and ideological purposes pose?

The research, which will be conducted based on these questions, aims to provide recommendations for the development of dark tourism in Azerbaijan in a more healthy, ethical and culturally sustainable way, both at the theoretical and practical levels. The results of the article may be useful for both the academic community and tourism policymakers and planners.

1. Methodology

This study was conducted within the framework of a qualitative research method to investigate the ethical and cultural aspects of dark tourism sites in Azerbaijan. The main goal of the study is to analyze the tourism potential of places associated with tragedy, death and historical trauma (for example, the Alley of Martyrs, the Guba Genocide Memorial Complex, the Khojaly Monument, etc.) and the ethical and cultural frameworks in relation to these sites.

The following methods were used during the research:

- Literature review – International and local sources (Lennon, 2000) related to dark tourism were examined, ethical and cultural approaches were analyzed comparatively.

- Content analysis – were analyzed texts on selected dark tourism objects, and were identified ethical and cultural messages.

- Symbolic interpretation – were interpreted visual and textual elements of memorial and monument objects with a semiotic approach, and was assessed their role in building collective memory and national identity. Within the framework of the article, was reviewed the "Eternal Torch" monument in the Alley of Martyrs. The visual and textual elements of this monument were interpreted with a semiotic approach. For example, elements such as the golden glass crown and the tomb on top of the monument are symbols of Azerbaijan's struggle for freedom and independence. The shape of the monument – an eight-pointed star and a torch inside – is interpreted as a national symbol that belongs to both history and the modern era. The monument also serves to preserve collective memory and national identity. The Alley of Martyrs is also considered a place that revives the memory of the Azerbaijani people and shapes the cultural experience of historical tragedies. These symbolic elements also demonstrate the cultural message (death, struggle, sacrifice, and memory) presented to tourists. Similarly, the Khojaly monument and the January 20 monument, each with its own symbolic and visual form, embody the historical contradictions and struggles of Azerbaijan. The visual structures of these monuments and the inscriptions on them are associated with a nationalist spiritual experience deeply rooted in society.

The main focus of the study was on the Azerbaijani context, and the results were discussed in a broad cultural framework. Because dark tourism has not only physical, but also spiritual and emotional aspects. In addition, the study, viewed from an intercultural perspective, allows us to determine Azerbaijan's place in this field by examining the dark tourism experiences of other countries. In the Azerbaijani context, these objects also occupy a special place in the formation of identity and the management of collective memory. At the same time, the study also took into account the subjective observations of the author. Were collected the author's personal observations, in particular, through field research and notes on the behavior of tourists. Interviews and visual observations help to reveal not only the physical impact of the analyzed objects, but also their psychological and emotional effects. For example, feelings of respect and sadness shown by tourists at the Alley of Martyrs and other memorial sites are supported not only by statistical data, but also by

subjective observations. These observations are important for revealing how visitor behavior is formed and the deep cultural meaning of these monuments.

2. Literature Review

Among the objects of dark tourism in Azerbaijan, the Alley of Martyrs, where the January 20 tragedy occurred, the Khojaly Genocide Memorial Complex, and the places destroyed during the Karabakh war or where martyrs were buried, occupy a special place. In local studies, these places are mostly studied in the context of patriotism and national memory. However, studies in the field of studying these objects from an ethical and cultural perspective within the framework of dark tourism have not yet been widely disseminated. Many authors emphasize that approaching the memory of the victims of the tragedy for tourist purposes may conflict with the moral values of society. In this regard, issues such as protecting ethical responsibility, preventing the risks of commercialization, and informing visitors become priority topics. In studies in Azerbaijan, these topics are still explained more with emotional and symbolic approaches.

Regarding the cultural aspects, dark tourism sites play an important role in the formation of collective memory, strengthening national identity and intergenerational transmission of historical events. In this context, Azerbaijani scholars and researchers have analyzed the Alley of Martyrs, the Khojaly Memorial and other similar sites as cultural symbols, showing their functions in ritualized propaganda and memory politics. At the same time, from a cultural perspective, questions such as how these sites are transformed into touristic experiences and how they are connected to the emotional reality and cultural context of the visitor remain open for scientific discussion. (Nadir & Sevda, 2022). Overall, the scientific literature on dark tourism in the Azerbaijani context is still in its early stages of development. Thus, during the research, it became clear that Azerbaijani researchers Habiba Soltanova studied the history of tourism in Azerbaijan (Soltanova, 2015), Ilgar Huseynov and Nigar Efendiyeva studied the scientific and cultural essence of tourism and its initial conditions (Hüseynov & Efendiyeva, 2007), and the conceptual framework of tourism (Bilalov, 2015) in the textbook prepared by the Center for Civic Initiatives within the framework of the project “Publication of the textbook “Fundamentals of Tourism” for the development of tourism education” implemented with the financial assistance of the Council for State Support to Non-Governmental Organizations under the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan. In addition, local studies examined the socio-cultural aspects of tourism (Cəfəri, 2013), socio-economic problems of tourism development (Əlirzayev & Aslanova,

2006) regulation of tourism activities (Bilalov, 2006). Deepening this field in terms of ethical and cultural aspects, comparative analysis of international approaches with local experiences, and at the same time studying the attitude of the local community towards this form of tourism create broad opportunities for research.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Ethical issues of dark tourism

The most widely discussed ethical dilemma of dark tourism is the commercialization of historical tragedies and collective traumas. This is called the "commodification of tragedy" and is particularly relevant when tragic sites are integrated into the tourism sector. (Light, 2017). In the Azerbaijani context, this issue is extremely sensitive. The Khojaly genocide, the massacres during the Karabakh wars, and the state of the destroyed cities after the war have left a deep mark on the country's collective memory. While the transformation of these sites into tourist attractions is considered useful in terms of informing the world community and preserving memory, on the other hand, the presentation of the tragedy as an "interesting place to see" may be a concern. In this regard, the ethical issue is not only the question of what to show, but also how to show it. Visitors should come to these sites not only for curiosity and emotional experience, but also to be informed and to build empathy. If these sites are presented simply as a photo opportunity or a "tourist point of interest", this would not only distort the essence of the tragedy, but could also be considered disrespectful to the memory of the victims. Therefore, in the context of Azerbaijan, the principles of non-commercial approaches, respect for cultural and religious values, fact-based narratives, and consultation with local communities should be strictly observed when presenting these sites. The preservation of historical events as part of national memory, not as a source of income, should form the basis of this balance.

One of the main components of dark tourism is the ethical issues surrounding how visitors behave in these places (Qasımlı & Məhəmmədli, 2024a). Such places are not only tourist destinations, but also places intended for remembrance, mourning and reflection. Therefore, visitors must adhere to certain norms of behavior when entering these places. Laughter, loud talking, frivolous posing for social media, unethical clothing and behavior are contrary to the essence of tragic events and can create social tension between visitors and local communities. Visitor education and the development of codes of ethics are essential to overcome this problem. Information boards at entry points, short video guides or mobile applications should inform visitors about the nature of these places and expected behavior.

It should also be ensured that guides adhere to these ethical standards and inform visitors. In short, visitor behavior in dark tourism places should be evaluated not only as a matter of individual responsibility, but also in the context of social and national responsibility. Without the right ethical framework in place, these spaces can lose their function and become a source of conflict.

Tourism companies play an important role in the development of dark tourism. Since they act as intermediaries between visitors and the place, they are responsible for both the transfer of information and the protection of ethical frameworks. This responsibility should be determined not only by commercial principles, but also by social and humanitarian obligations (Prindle Institute for Ethics, 2021.) In the context of Azerbaijan, especially to the Karabakh region, companies organizing tourist trips should both correctly present historical truths and shape the attitude of visitors to these places. This should not be just an "excursion", but also an educational and emotional preparation process. Providing superficial information about tragic places or relying only on visual effects can deprive tourism of its informative and spiritual functions.

3.2. Culturological aspects of dark tourism

Dark tourism is not only associated with the commemoration of tragic events, but also has an important function in terms of preserving historical memory and preserving cultural identity (Carrigan, 2014). Especially in countries with a rich and turbulent history like Azerbaijan, this type of tourism allows us to uncover important layers of culture and pass them on to future generations.

In the modern history of Azerbaijan, the Khojaly genocide, the Karabakh wars, deportations and other tragic events are not only historical facts, but also the main components of national and cultural memory (Mahamadli, 2018). The places where these events took place – that is, dark tourism objects – are not only tourist attractions, but also places of identity and memory. In these places, the process of forming national identity, remembering and processing collective trauma, and at the same time drawing cultural lessons for the future takes place. When preserving these places and presenting them to visitors, it is very important to present historical truths without falsification, in a transparent and honest way. Visitors should get acquainted not only with the consequences of the events in these places, but also with their causes, social and cultural contexts.

To ensure this, cultural heritage institutions, museums, scientific centers and local communities should be involved in this presentation process. Dark tourism can also ensure

the aesthetic preservation of memory through the integration of historical experiences into culture. For example, through exhibitions, film festivals, educational programs and community projects dedicated to tragedies, this memory can be perpetuated and communicated to a wider audience. Mourning tourism is not only an individual emotional experience, but also an important cultural tool in terms of the formation of collective identity and nationalism. Thus, through mourning tourism, the painful events experienced by the people in the past become a symbol of unity, an example of national determination, and this has a strong impact on the formation of public opinion and the national spirit. This is very clearly seen in the example of Azerbaijan (Muhammadli, 2023). The cities, destroyed mosques and other symbolic objects destroyed by the Armenians during the Karabakh war are both an indicator of losses and a reflection of the will of the Azerbaijani people to resist and revive. Tourist trips organized to these objects do not only serve an informational purpose, but also strengthen feelings of national pride and patriotism. Visitors in these places both get acquainted with historical events and witness the difficult path the people have gone through. At the same time, political and ideological messages of the state can also be transmitted through mourning tourism. For example, the restoration work carried out in the Azerbaijani lands liberated from the Armenian occupation and visits to these areas emphasize not only nostalgia and sadness, but also the idea of victory and revival. This can strengthen Azerbaijan's cultural and political position both domestically and internationally. However, respect for ethnic and religious diversity, the preservation of cultural pluralism, and the maintenance of historical objectivity are important conditions in this process. Otherwise, mourning tourism may lead to social polarization instead of strengthening national unity.

Dark tourism causes a number of changes in cultural and social spheres. These changes are manifested both in individual values and in social relations (Mahammadi, 2024). Visits to tragic places form empathy, understanding and a more sensitive approach to history among people. This, in turn, affects the development of social justice, historical responsibility and civic consciousness.

The social impacts of dark tourism in Azerbaijan are gradually beginning to manifest themselves (Məhəmmədli, 2024). For example, visits to liberated territories are important not only for paying homage to the martyrs, but also for the rehabilitation of local communities and for social cohesion. These visits create conditions for the territories to be

associated not only with war memories, but also with reconstruction and the restoration of life.

Through dark tourism, concepts such as historical thinking, respect for cultural values, and social responsibility can be more strongly formed in younger generations. Educational tours organized at the school and university level are useful tools in this regard. Such trips become not only an excursion for pupils and students, but also an important experience in terms of personal development and citizenship (Qasımlı & Məhəmmədli, 2024b). At the same time, the popularization of dark tourism is also giving rise to new cultural initiatives, public projects, and creative activities. Art exhibitions, literary competitions, documentaries, and social media campaigns related to tragic events create conditions for culture to engage in a more active dialogue with these events.

3.3. Dark tourism sites

Dark tourism sites – sometimes called "dark heritage sites" – are places associated with tragic, traumatic, or deadly events in the past. These sites provide visitors with an opportunity to engage with historical memory and reflect on human tragedies (Stone, 2006). They offer both historical education and emotional experiences. Dark tourism sites are used not only to commemorate tragedies, but also to convey messages of peace and tolerance, to learn from history, to pass on information to future generations, and to promote social justice.

Although the concept of dark tourism is widespread worldwide, its application in the Azerbaijani context is relatively new. However, the numerous conflicts, tragedies, and social traumas that have occurred in the country's history and modern times provide rich spaces and deep content for this type of tourism. These objects act not only as symbols of grief and pain, but also as a means of preserving historical memory, strengthening cultural identity, and restoring historical justice.

There are important public spaces in the construction and continuity of Azerbaijan's common memory, in the commercialization of the past for the "present" and "future". Examples of this are the "Martyrs' Alley", the "Alley of Honor" and the "Guba Genocide Complex" (Guliyeva, 2022) These spaces, as public spaces built in the name of common memory, can be classified in two different ways: while the "Martyrs' Alley" and the "Guba Genocide Complex" exist as representatives of grief, death and tragedy, the "Alley of Honor" is closer to the concept of "dead heroes" as defined by Walter (2009).

3.4. Interpretation of dark tourism objects

The interpretation of dark tourism objects is carried out through their physical design, forms of information presentation and the relationship established with the visitor. These objects are not only historical places to be visited, but also have the function of preserving cultural memory, promoting ethics and providing historical lessons. Therefore, the planning and presentation of these places to the public must be carried out in an extremely sensitive and purposeful manner.

In the context of Azerbaijan, places with tragic history such as Khojaly, Shusha, Agdam are considered the main directions of dark tourism. Presentations in these areas should be not only informative, but also emotionally and aesthetically thought out. The design of the spaces should clearly express the scale of the tragedy, its historical and social context, and the stories of the victims. Museums, memorial complexes, open-air exhibitions are the most important structures that can serve this purpose.

Visual materials – photographs, maps, documents, videos and documentaries – should be used extensively in exhibitions. However, the selection and use of these materials should be carried out within an ethical framework. The main principle should be that tragic images are presented not for the purpose of emotional manipulation, but for the purpose of educating and creating empathy. For example, personal stories of victims, family memories, letters and other personal artifacts strengthen the humanizing approach (Ismayilov & Khalafova, 2022a).

Dynamic presentation methods are also important in tragic places. Interactive exhibits, audiovisual guides, and virtual reality technologies can provide visitors with the opportunity to experience historical events more deeply. These technologies should be applied not only to arouse interest, but also to establish an emotional connection with history. For example, presenting the memories of a soldier who participated in the Karabakh battles in audio format or restoring a historical site that once existed through 3D modeling can provide visitors with both an informative and emotional experience (Kushzhanov & Dashgin, 2019a). Cultural symbols also play a large role in these objects. The background of Azerbaijani folk music, the use of architectural details with national ornaments, and the appropriate integration of the flag and symbolic images help to emphasize national identity. However, all these elements must be implemented in a balanced way so that the presentation of the tragedy remains level-headed and respectful.

The behavior and attitudes of visitors to tragic sites are crucial to the ethical and cultural sustainability of dark tourism. The ultimate goal should be for visitors to become not just observers but also learners, understanders, and respectful participants in these sites. This is only possible through education (Kushzhanov & Dashqin, 2019a). In the newly developing field of dark tourism for Azerbaijan, it is important to systematically organize this issue. Each dark tourism facility should provide clear instructions at the entrance about the rules of ethical behavior, principles of permission to take photos, and zones where silence and are required respect. For example, in the Khojaly memorial complex or in the new museums that have started operating in Shusha, codes of ethics can be placed in the form of boards.

Ethical norms can be explained through educational materials, guidebooks, mobile applications, and audio guides for visitors (Kushzhanov & Mahammadli, 2019b). These materials should emphasize the historical context of the tragedy, as well as the lessons of humanity, tolerance, and peace. At the same time, specific behavioral patterns should be provided – for example, refraining from speaking loudly, not damaging the site, refraining from taking selfies and posing funny, etc.

It is possible to provide in-depth information to visitors through educational packages and tourist programs at tragic sites. For example, specially designed educational excursions, seminars, and interactive classes can be organized for schools and universities. These programs can integrate and present various subjects related to history, ethical behavior, and cultural memory.

Educational programs should be designed not only for local visitors, but also for international tourists (Khalafova & Ismailov, 2024). For this purpose, materials should be prepared in different languages, professional guides should be trained, and an appropriate approach should be applied for each group. For example, the history of the Karabakh war can be explained to a European tourist not only in a political context, but also from the perspective of human rights and international humanitarian law. Visitor education should also be linked to increasing social responsibility, drawing lessons from tragedies, and providing messages to prevent such incidents from happening again in the future. This shows that dark tourism is not only about the past, but also has the function of building a culture of peace, cooperation, and understanding for the future.

The interpretation of dark tourism objects is not limited to technical and visual presentation. The ethical, cultural and educational aspects of these objects should be

developed in an integrated manner. For Azerbaijan, this direction is of strategic importance both in terms of preserving national memory and transmitting accurate and valuable messages to a global audience. The main principle in the presentation of dark tourism objects is respect and empathy. These places should never be used for entertainment or commercial purposes. Especially in countries like Azerbaijan that are still experiencing a post-conflict rehabilitation period, it would be more appropriate to use these places to call for peace, support unity and promote historical justice. At the same time, these places should be based on the principle of a multicultural approach, protection of cultural diversity and respect for human rights. The presentations should avoid one-sided rhetoric of revenge and focus on historical objectivity and human feelings.

Dark tourism sites in Azerbaijan are of great importance in terms of both not forgetting the tragic events of the past and transmitting deep historical lessons to future generations. Through these sites, the country's historical traumas can be presented to the global community, as well as strengthening collective memory, national identity and peace messages for the domestic audience (İsmayılov & Məhəmmədli, 2024). The development of this field based on ethical and culturological approaches promises valuable results for both the tourism sector and society.

3.5. Martyrs' Alley

A mass grave where the martyrs of January 20 and the Karabakh War are buried (Gəraylı, 2011). After Azerbaijan gained independence from the USSR, was demolished the monument to Kirov in the Martyrs' Alley. The appeal of Doctor of Sciences Azer Nəbiyev, who spoke on behalf of the burial commission created by the public in 1990 to bury the people who died for the independence of Azerbaijan in the current Martyrs' Alley, was not positively responded to. On January 20-21, graves were dug in the alley. More than 120 graves were dug and prepared. On January 21, a meeting of the Supreme Soviet of the Azerbaijan SSR was held. The meeting took place in very tense conditions, with heated struggles. Discussions were held until 6:00 in the morning. At 12:00, the bodies of the martyrs were carried on the shoulders of people from Azadlıq Square through the streets of the capital to the current Alley of Martyrs (Kenzhebayeva, Urmurzina & Mahammadli, 2018). The funeral ceremony lasted 5 hours. On January 22, were buried 51 people. 3 of them were martyrs during the March 1918 genocide. They were also buried according to tradition. The words "Martyrs of 1918" were written on all three graves. Then, when new gravestones were erected, the word "Unknown" was written on those graves. Among the

martyrs of Black January, there was one unknown 25-year-old young man, and he was buried last. Currently, there are 159 graves in the Alley of Martyrs. Of these graves, 97 have headstones (including 4 unknown graves, 1 grave without a picture), 62 graves do not have headstones, only are inscribed the pictures and names of the martyrs. The 62 martyrs mentioned were buried in other areas. The Martyrs' Mosque in the Alley was built in 1996 by a Turkish organization called the Dayanat Foundation. From 2009 to 2017, the mosque was closed for renovation.

The idea of creating the "Eternal Flame" monument complex was first put forward in 1994. On August 5, 1998, the great leader Heydar Aliyev issued a decree on the erection of the "Eternal Torch" monument complex in the Alley of Martyrs in Baku. (Baku city..., 1998) The order instructs the Baku City Executive Power to ensure the construction of the "Eternal Flame" monument complex, and the Cabinet of Ministers to submit a proposal to allocate 2 billion manats for the construction of the monument complex (Ismayılov & Khudiyeva, 2023). Thus, the construction of the monument complex begins. In the competition for the construction of the complex, was selected the project developed by the design company led by architect Elbay Gasimzadeh.

The monument complex was inaugurated on October 9, 1998. Located on the Alley of Martyrs, this monument consists of a crypt (tomb) crowned with a golden glass dome standing on an 8-pointed star (Karabalina, Maydangalieva, Satygalieva, Ahmetalina, & Mahammadli, 2018). The elegant network decorating the walls of the crypt gives the monumental structure a certain lightness and airy transparency. In 2007, by order of President İlham Aliyev, during the reconstruction of the Alley of Martyrs, the columns of the "Eternal Flame" monument were raised, and the eight-pointed star and the pores of the eight-pointed mirror on the monument were decorated with gold (Yunusov, 2010).

3.6. Alley of Martyrs II

Founded in 2018, it is an alley where servicemen of the Azerbaijani Armed Forces who died for their special services in preserving and are buried restoring the territorial integrity of Azerbaijan. The cemetery is located on the territory of Alley of Honor No. 2. More than 100 martyrs of the 44-day Patriotic War are buried in the Alley of Martyrs II. Of those buried here, 1 is a major general, 2 are lieutenant generals, 1 is a colonel, 13 are lieutenant colonels, and 15 are majors.

3.7. Guba Genocide Memorial Complex

It was erected in memory of tens of thousands of Azerbaijanis who died as a result of the mass massacres carried out by Bolshevik-Armenian armed groups on Azerbaijani lands in 1918. On December 30, 2009, the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev signed a decree on the establishment of the “Genocide Memorial Complex” in the city of Guba in order to convey to the world community the territorial claims and aggressive policy of Armenian nationalists against Azerbaijan, their bloody crimes, to preserve the national memory of future generations and to perpetuate the memory of the victims of the genocide (Guba, 2009) On September 18, 2013, the opening of the Guba Genocide Memorial Complex took place with the participation of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev and his wife Mehriban Aliyeva. The total area of the complex is 3.5 hectares and consists of 5 parts.

- Memorial Monument (the burial place of human bones from the discovered cemetery)
- Symbolic cemetery
- Genocide Museum
- Flag Square
- Information Center Mass grave (Ismayilov & Khalafova, 2022b).

The monument consists of three parts: two structures resembling sharp knives - the entrance and exit, and the main hall with a black memorial stone in the center. The sharp points of the monument embody severe pain. The fact that the sharp points emerge from under the ground reflects the impossibility of hiding the truth. The monument is made entirely of brotto-concrete. In order to embody the silence of mourning in memory of the victims of the tragedy, the project refused any decoration. The exposition of the monument-museum reflects the history of the genocide of the Muslim population in 5 districts of the Baku province - Baku, Shamakhi, Guba, Javad and Goychay in March-July 1918. The museum exposition, consisting of 19 sections, is presented in Azerbaijani, Russian and English.

The exposition begins with photographs reflecting the peaceful life of Guba on the eve of the events of 1918. Are exhibited, here, photographs reflecting the life of ancient Guba, representatives of Azerbaijanis, Lezgi, Jews and other peoples living peacefully side by side, people belonging to different social classes. (Kazimi & Mahammadli, 2021). The exposition is rich in unique archival documents. Here, the decision of the Azerbaijan Democratic

Republic to establish the Extraordinary Investigation Commission to investigate the crime after the bloody events of 1918 and the documents of the commission are presented, a map with special content reflecting the territory of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic in 1918-1920, and Heydar Aliyev's decree on genocide. During the genocides that occurred in various districts, most of the people who were killed with particular cruelty were burned, thrown into the sea, wells, and therefore it was not possible to bury them. A black marble stone was erected in the center of the hall in memory of such victims (Ismayilov, Mahammadli & Gasimli, 2023b). The Museum Complex has an information center, a rich library, and a reading room equipped with computers. The National Flag of the Republic of Azerbaijan has been raised on the territory of the complex. An orchard consisting of apple trees, the symbol of Guba, has been planted in the spacious courtyard. The historical tragedy of each district is presented in separate sections in the museum with rich photos, archival documents, statistical information and diagrams. All information is reflected in the electronic database installed in front of each section in three languages.

A documentary film reflecting the Guba genocide is continuously shown in the hall. The exposition is complemented by a modern art piece – human faces reflected on a giant metal plate. This is considered to be a modern view of the events that have been absorbed into the blood memory of history, an attitude of the modern era. The exit of the hall is completed with photographs reflecting the liberation of Baku by the Caucasian Islamic Army in 1918.

3.8. Memorial Genocide Museum at the Military Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Azerbaijan

Museum The opening of the Memorial Genocide Museum took place on February 24, 2014 in the administrative building of the Military Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Azerbaijan (Ismayilov & Aliyeva, 2023). The museum consists of 4 sections: history, deportation-repression, genocide and terrorism, and is located on an area of only 320 square meters. The paintings placed at the entrance to the museum reflect the mourning silence of the victims of the genocide. The museum is equipped with a rich book fund consisting of books by foreign and Azerbaijani authors about the genocide, deportation, and war crimes committed against our people. Employees of the Institute of History and the Military Prosecutor's Office are preparing new books based on documents and investigation materials stored in the "Memorial Genocide Museum".

3.9. A monument in memory of Ottoman and Azerbaijani soldiers who died in the March massacres of 1918 in Hajigabul

A monument was erected in memory of Ottoman and Azerbaijani soldiers who died in the March massacres of 1918 in the village of Gubalı Baloglan, Hajigabul. In 1918, 6 soldiers of the Caucasian Islamic Army and 6 Azerbaijani soldiers who fought shoulder to shoulder with them were martyred in the battle against Armenian-Dashnak armed formations in the village of Gubalı Baloglan. Village resident Hanifa Movlayev, who witnessed the massacres, buried the martyred soldiers, whose names are still unknown today, in her yard. With the financial support of the Turkish Embassy in Azerbaijan, a monument was erected on the graves in memory of Ottoman and Azerbaijani soldiers, and the graves were renovated and renovated.

It should be noted that a lot of work has been done to immortalize the 1918 genocide in various cities and villages of Azerbaijan. Examples of this include the monument complex erected in memory of the victims of the March 31 genocide in Salyan, the monument erected in the name of the people killed in the village of Narimankend in Shamakhi, the monument erected in the name of the people killed in the village of Gemustu in the same region in 1918 (Qəniyev, 2003), and the monument to two Turkish soldiers who died in secondary school No. 123 named after H. Z. Tagiyev in Baku.

3.10. Khojaly Genocide Memorial Complex

During the First Karabakh War (1991–1994), which began with the military aggression of the Republic of Armenia against the Republic of Azerbaijan, Armenia occupied and destroyed Eastern Zangezur and Karabakh, and committed the most serious international crimes against the Azerbaijani people. (İsmayılov, Mahammadli & Gasimli, 2023a). The crime of genocide committed on ethnic grounds against the civilian population during the occupation of the city of Khojaly on February 26, 1992 is the bloodiest page of the conflict. Steps at the national level to ensure that the Khojaly genocide receives its true legal value and that the world is aware of such a crime were taken after the return to power of the National Leader of the Azerbaijani people Heydar Aliyev. By the decision of the Milli Majlis dated February 24, 1994, February 26 was declared Khojaly Genocide Day and international organizations were informed about this. Thanks to the courage and heroism of the Azerbaijani Army in the 44-day Patriotic War in September-November 2020 and the one-day local anti-terrorist operation in September 2023, our historical lands, including the Khojaly region, were liberated from occupation, and the Azerbaijani Flag

was raised in Khojaly on October 15, 2023. Guided by Clause 32 of Article 109 of the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan, on February 25, 2025, the Head of State signed a decree on the establishment of the Khojaly Genocide Memorial Complex in the city of Khojaly of the Republic of Azerbaijan in order to internationally promote the genocide committed against the Azerbaijani people and perpetuate the dear memory of the victims of the Khojaly tragedy (Khojaly city, 2025).

3.11. Mother's Cry (monument)

In the “Mother’s Cry” monument erected in 1993, a young woman, a symbol of the women of Khojaly, lifts her baby, who was killed by Armenian executioners, on her head. This image reflects both help, a cry, and accusation (Ismayilov & Khalafova, 2023). As if the representative of the women of Khojaly, who experienced the same fate, accuses the whole world and demands an answer from them. In the monument erected in 1993, the mother is as mobile as the women of Khojaly who escaped from the Armenians. The clothes of the depicted mother reflect the pain and suffering of the women of Khojaly, who walked through the forests and rivers on a snowy and frosty night. In that monument, the woman is barefoot.

The second statue is made of bronze and black granite. The height of the monument is 8.6 m, and the height of the statue is 3.2 m. The statue depicts a mother who was forced to flee from home in a nightgown and clutching her dead baby to her heart. Photos taken by the National Hero of Azerbaijan Chingiz Mustafayev were also used during the preparation of the statue (Ismayilov, Mahammadli & Khudiyeva, 2022). The bas-reliefs placed on the pedestal of the monument depict women, children, and the elderly killed during the genocide, as well as Chingiz Mustafayev himself, who took a camera to photograph the dead baby. At the bottom of the pedestal are numerical facts about the genocide and a list of those killed. There have been no significant changes in the content of the monument complex. In both statues, the mother holds her murdered baby in her arms. It's just that in the first statue, the mother is depicted with the baby on her head, and was inaugurated in the second - on her arms On February 26, 2008, the new monument.

3.12. Patriotic War Memorial Complex

The establishment of the Patriotic War Memorial Complex and Victory Park was carried out in accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev signed on December 3, 2020, in order to preserve the unparalleled heroism shown by the Azerbaijani people in the Patriotic War and the magnificent historical Victory

they won, to demonstrate it to the public, and to perpetuate the dear memory of our martyrs. (Baku city, 2020). Victory Park covers an area of about 10 hectares. At the entrance to the park is the Victory Arch. The location of the Victory Arch is also the intersection of two roads leading to the city center. As a symbol of the 44-day Patriotic War, the Victory Arch is 44 meters high, 22 meters wide, and has 44 columns. The arches symbolically depict the beginning of the road leading to Victory. The tree element at the top of the arch is intended to create the image of a growing Azerbaijan, flourishing, prosperity, a new life, and a symbolic road leading to Victory. At the entrance to the park, has been erected the Victory Monument, reflecting November 8 - Victory Day,. This memorial monument embodies two powerful symbols: Victory Day and unbreakable unity as a symbol of eternity. The greenery around the monument reflects the patterns and decorative elements of Karabakh carpets. The lower part of the park, the Victory Museum, has already been built. It is currently being designed. There will be two entrances to the museum from the park. The "Iron Fist" symbol will be created at the main entrance to the museum. The history of the Victory will be commemorated on this symbol. The "Iron Fist" is considered a symbol of the unity of the Leader, the People, the State and the Army, which is the basis of the Victory. The purpose of creating the Victory Museum is to keep alive the memory of the road to the historical Victory for the liberation of the Azerbaijani lands, the soldiers and officers who fought heroically in the Patriotic War, and all the martyrs. The name of each of the martyrs of the Patriotic War will be engraved in the Victory Museum. The exhibits to be collected in the museum will demonstrate the courage of the soldiers and officers who participated in the war and the determination of the Azerbaijani people. The park also features a thematic garden, a cascade waterfall, a Karabakh memorial garden, and a general observation point for the park, and recreation areas have been built around the memorial garden. At the end of the park is the Freedom Flag Square. The Azerbaijani Flag will fly in the center of the water basin. The path to the Freedom Flag Square, consisting of 44 bronze slabs, will serve as a symbol of the Patriotic War.

3.13. The Occupation and Victory Museum Complex in Karabakh

In the Eastern Zangezur and Karabakh regions of Azerbaijan, which were liberated from the thirty-year Armenian occupation, our ancestral lands have been subjected to vandalism, and our historical and cultural heritage has been razed to the ground. According to the instructions of President Ilham Aliyev, the Occupation and Victory Museum Complexes are being created in the regions and cities liberated from the occupation (Heydar,

2023). One of such museum complexes is being created in Lachin. The complex to be built in the Lachin district will consist of the Occupation and Victory museums, and a memorial park where the ruins will be displayed. The logo of the complex symbolizes the juniper trees that are widespread in the Lachin district, which has a mysterious beauty and natural wealth. The area selected for the complex, which will have a total area of 3.5 hectares, is located on a slope. From here, a beautiful view opens up to the city of Lachin and the surrounding mountains. The complex is located close to the main road network and the city center.

The museum building has an architectural structure that is distinguished by its majestic and aesthetic beauty. Thus, the building's extension towards the slope of the hill expresses stability and durability. Symbolically, the structure of the building embodies the ascent towards the sky, drawing strength from the ground. Thanks to the sloping shape of the building, which partially passes into the underground part, the total internal area of the museum is 2400 square meters (Ismayilov, 2022). The interior of the museum has been specially designed to provide easy access from all sides and to integrate with the surrounding park. The building, which harmonizes with the terrain, will feature two panoramic terraces on the roof, accessible both from the inside of the building via an elevator and from Memorial Park. The museum, which will consist of five floors, will have a spacious lobby with a ticket sales center and administrative rooms on the first floor. The Occupation Museum will be located on the second floor, a cafe on the third floor, and the Victory Museum on the fourth floor. The last - fifth floor will house a lobby consisting of a recreation hall and a bookstore and providing access to the building from the upper part, and a Memorial Park will be built on the territory of the Complex, where the remains of many destroyed historical and cultural monuments of the city will be exhibited. The ruins included in the Memorial Park will be enriched with artistic installations and turned into an open-air museum.

The Gubadli Occupation and Victory Museum Complex will consist of the Occupation Museum, the Victory Museum and the Memorial Park consisting of ruins. The complex will cover an area of approximately 3 hectares. This area is in a very strategic position, close to the main road network and transport junction. Also, part of the natural green belt surrounding the Hakari River will form the northern part of the complex's territory, which in turn will allow the complex to be built in a stunning natural environment. Since part of the river passes through the territory of the complex, it is planned to symbolically connect the Victory Museum and the Occupation Museum with each other through a beautiful scenic bridge.

Many ancient bridges, such as the Lalazar Bridge built over the Hakari River, and the spiral horns depicted on stone ram figures discovered in the Gubadli area, are the main sources of inspiration for the project concept (Ismayilov, Ismayilov & Mammadova, 2019). The building of the Occupation Museum begins with a spiral path rising from the right bank of a small river.

This path spirals along the building area, then continues over the river, turns into a beautiful scenic bridge and ends at a spiral staircase connecting to the Victory Museum on the left bank of the river. The interior of the Gubadli Occupation Museum is characterized by the spiral shape of the building. The museum's exposition will be organized using various audio and visual technologies. The museum will visually demonstrate the daily life of the population in Gubadli before the occupation, the occupation of the city and the memories of witnesses of those events, the destroyed heritage and the vandalism that the area was subjected to after the occupation. A terrace consisting of greenery will be organized on the last floor of the museum building for visitors to relax. The interior of the Victory Museum will also be circular (Balginova, Maydangalieva, Satygalieva & Mahammadli, 2018). The exhibition halls located on the first floor will be dedicated to the heroism shown by our people and the Victory gained, including the "Iron Fist" operation. An exposition will be created on the second floor, using visual technologies, perpetuating the dear memory of the martyrs who gave their lives for the Motherland and presenting information about our heroes. The museum will also feature a special hall for holding various exhibitions. From here, visitors will be able to climb both the stairs and the elevator to the open-air amphitheater on the upper floor, which is intended for organizing various cultural events.

The Zangilan Occupation and Victory Museum complex will consist of the Occupation Museum, the Victory Museum, and a Memorial Park reflecting the ruins. The Occupation Museum aims to visually demonstrate the vandalism suffered by the city and the region during the enemy's occupation. It is planned that a certain part of Zangilan city will remain in a destroyed state and will be displayed as an open-air museum reflecting the general picture of Armenia's occupation policy (Ismayilov & Bayramova, 2022b). The Occupation Museum will bring to attention information about the ecological damage caused to the environment, especially the acts of ecological terrorism committed in Zangilan city with the aim of causing serious damage to the environment, biodiversity, forests, underground and surface natural resources. The museum's exposition will be organized using various audio and visual technologies. The images and patterns on the facade of the museum building,

which will be made of glass, will resemble a plane tree leaf, which will glorify the close connection of Zangilan city with nature.

The Zangilan Victory Museum will be a complex that immortalizes the determination, courage and professionalism demonstrated by the Azerbaijani people and our glorious Army during the 44-day Patriotic War, as well as a place that conveys the achieved Victory to people with modern presentation methods. The facade of the Victory Museum building, reminiscent of a plane tree forest, will be dedicated to the Zangilan forests, the second largest natural plane tree forest in the world by area. The museum's lobby will be used as an exhibition space to display information dedicated to the Victory through visual technologies. A 4D cinema with 80 seats will also be created in the museum. One of the main goals in the construction of this museum is to organize the "Zangilan Earth Film Festival" here in the future and bring the ecological terrorism committed in Zangilan to the attention of the international community. In order to immortalize the dear memory of our martyrs who gave their lives for the territorial integrity of Azerbaijan, a "Memorial Plaque" will be created next to the Victory Museum building in the form of a concrete fence with the names of our heroes. A special project will be implemented to creatively reflect historical facts about Zangilan on the ruins. Artists from different countries of the world will create different murals ("Street art") on the ruins. Thus, an open-air exhibition will be organized along the Memorial Park, which consists of ruins covering an area of 10,500 square meters.

3.14. Bullet-riddled monuments in Shusha

The statues of famous Azerbaijani figures, including poetess Khurshudbanu Natavan, composer Uzeyir Hajibeyli, and singer Bulbul, who were shot dead, are now located in the central square in the city of Shusha (Mammadov, 2022b). Once upon a time, these monuments were the decoration of the city of Shusha, the cradle of culture of the Karabakh region. On May 8, 1992, the Karabakh region, including the city of Shusha, was occupied by the Armenian armed forces.

At that time, everything in the city of Shusha became a victim of Armenian vandalism. The Armenians destroyed and looted museums, monuments, mosques, cultural centers, and cemeteries in Shusha. The statues were not left out of this act of vandalism. Not content with killing civilians, the Armenian invaders also aimed their weapons at statues and busts belonging to Azerbaijanis. As a result, the busts of three great Azerbaijani personalities in Shusha were pierced with holes. By shooting and insulting the statues, the Armenians also ignored the requirements of the International Hague Convention (Askerova & Mammadov,

2025). The Armenians, who were greedy for the bronze material of those statues, melted them down and took them from Shusha to the Armenian capital of Yerevan, and from there to Georgia, in order to make money. Fortunately, these statues accidentally came across Azerbaijanis living in Georgia (Mammadov, 2013). Those Azerbaijanis immediately informed the relevant state bodies of Azerbaijan about the monuments. In 1993, at the initiative of the then President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the late Heydar Aliyev, those statues were bought for money and brought to Baku and temporarily placed in the courtyard of the National Museum of Art. The Azerbaijani government spent \$500,000 to buy back the “Bullested Statues” and bring them to Baku in 1993. In Baku, the “Bullested Statues” were among the exhibits that attracted the attention of foreign tourists for years. The Statues remained as displaced monuments in Baku from 1993 to 2021. Every year, during the ceremonies held on September 18 - National Music Day, the “Bullested Statues” in the courtyard of the Art Museum were also visited. Foreign guests visiting Azerbaijan and the National Art Museum were also informed about the “Bullested Statues”.

On January 14, 2021, the “Bullested Statues” were returned to Shusha with the participation of Azerbaijani President Ilham Aliyev. Supreme Commander-in-Chief Ilham Aliyev removed the veil from the bronze monument of three great personalities returned to the city of Shusha, thus restoring historical justice (Güllələnmiş heykeller, 2024).

Conclusions

The results of the study show that dark tourism is not only an area of activity that attracts the interest of tourists, but also plays an important role in preserving national memory and forming a collective identity. Although ethical questions arise regarding the use of these objects for commercial purposes in Azerbaijan, their cultural and emotional impact is significant. These monuments play a kind of therapeutic role by presenting people with deep meanings of tragedy and struggle, reliving traumas in the history of the people. The study also showed that the visual and textual elements of these objects, through symbolic interpretation, are important tools that strengthen national identity and keep cultural memory alive. The forms of monuments and the messages on them form a language that shows respect for historical events and the memory of martyrs. In addition, the results obtained as a result of subjective observations and empirical data revealed that tourists' attitudes towards these places are more emotional and sad (Mammadov, 2022a). The cultural messages presented by memorial sites and monuments have a strong impact not only on tourists, but also on the collective memory and cultural identity of the local population. Finally, the

results of the study indicate that a solid foundation has been created for Azerbaijan to further advance in the field of dark tourism and for in-depth research into the ethical and cultural aspects of this field.

Proper regulation of practices in this area is important both for tourism development and for the preservation of the culture of the people. In this regard,

- It is important to deepen ethical issues and develop control mechanisms related to memorial monuments and tourist sites related to the history and culture of Azerbaijan. The use of these objects for commercial purposes should be directed correctly, not distorting the memory of the nation, and based on legal regulations. For example, in places such as the Alley of Martyrs, it should be ensured that the experiences offered to tourists are in line with cultural and spiritual values.

- The cultural educational role of the place should be further developed in dark tourism sites. In addition to simply providing visitors with historical information, educational programs related to the history and collective memory of the nation should be organized. For example, more in-depth analyses should be provided regarding the January 20 events and the Khojaly genocide, so that tourists can better understand the social and emotional impacts of these events.

- It is important to present the symbolic and visual elements in memorial sites in a clear and understandable manner, based on more semiotic interpretations. The symbolic content of monuments, images, inscriptions and other visual elements should be correctly conveyed to tourists, and innovative presentation methods should be applied in order to increase the cultural impact of these objects.

- In connection with the development of digital culture, it is recommended to deliver information about dark tourism objects to a wider audience through internet resources. It is possible to provide visitors with more in-depth information and strengthen their cultural memory through virtual tours, interactive websites and social media platforms. Such resources should also be provided with multilingual support for foreign tourists.

- It is important to involve local communities more in the management of dark tourism objects and the experiences offered at these objects. It is precisely the experiences of the local population in preserving history and culture that will help to provide tourists with more authentic and in-depth information. Introducing these objects with the experiences of local communities in the field of tourism will also increase economic benefits.

- By offering social and cultural programs to visitors of dark tourism objects, it can be ensured that these objects are transformed not only as tourist activities, but also into cultural experiences and education. Also, seminars, lectures or art exhibitions can be organized in these facilities so that visitors can get acquainted with history and feel the richness of culture.

- A balance should be created regarding the commercial use of dark tourism facilities. It is important to implement commercial and educational use of these facilities at the same time. For example, monuments and memorials should be part of tourism activities, but at the same time, it should be ensured that people gain a wider knowledge of history and culture through educational programs, seminars and presentations.

These recommendations are designed to emphasize the need for greater attention to the ethical and culturological aspects of the dark tourism sector and how these facilities can be more useful for the preservation of national identity and culture. Developments in these areas will help both the local population and tourists to better understand and respect cultural values.

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